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TDK REPORT

Classification through Enhanced Adaptive Hybrid Feature Selection using Genetic Algorithms

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Abstract

Machine learning has several fields of application, such as pattern recognition and value prediction, in which it surpasses more traditional methods. However, as the dimensionality of data increases, so do the time and computational capacity requirements of the learning process. Feature selection is a method through which the dimension of data is reduced, thereby reducing model training costs and improving accuracy. The subject of this research is the introduction of a genetic search algorithm to an existing feature selection algorithm named Adaptive, Hybrid Feature Selection. Combining several measures, the AHFS algorithm is capable of achieving higher model accuracy than individual feature selection algorithms. By replacing the Sequential Forward Selection method present in the original AHFS with a genetic search algorithm, the greedy nature of SFS can be avoided, thus further increasing accuracy. Results indicate that the genetic algorithm has the potential of providing improved prediction rate when SFS prediction rate drops, however further research is necessary.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The emergence of machine learning and its increasingly widespread usage was accompanied by higher data dimensionality through the years. Big data is coined as a term for datasets of great size and complexity. With the increase of dimensions, the amount of data either also increases or becomes more sparse. This is called the curse of dimensionality, originally attributed to mathematician Richard Bellman[1]. For instance, in machine learning applications the increase in the number of features can be accompanied by model overfitting caused by the sparsity of data.

To combat these problems, the main solution is the reduction of dimensions to viable levels. In machine learning, feature selection and feature extraction are two groups of dimensionality reduction techniques that can be used. In general, feature extraction methods work primarily by transforming the original data, while feature selection aims to choose a small subset of relevant features from the original data by filtering out irrelevant, redundant and noisy features based on different measures.

The solution presented in this report is a feature selection algorithm called Adaptive, Hybrid Feature Selection[2] which utilizes several feature selection algorithms with different measures of selection in a unified framework. In the original AHFS algorithm, Sequential Forward Selection was used as a method for selecting relevant features. However, given the sequential nature of this technique, SFS is a greedy algorithm that may only achieve a local extremum for any evaluation metric and consequently fail to find the global extremum. The subject of this report is to replace SFS with a genetic algorithm that, by introducing mutation with a random chance, has the potential of achieving the optimal result.

The report first looks into the relevant literature of feature selection and search algorithms in Chapter 2. In Chapter 3, the proposed algorithm is documented in detail.

In Chapter 4, the achieved results are presented and compared to the original algorithm. Finally, in Chapter 5, the report is concluded and possible future works are considered.

Chapter 2

Literature review

This chapter is concerned with reviewing the literature relevant to this topic. In Section 1, the concept of feature selection and applied solutions are shown. In Section 2, measures and algorithms applied in feature selection, based on information theory and several others, are presented. Finally, in Section 3, search algorithms used in feature selection solutions are explored.

2.1. Feature selection solutions

Feature selection is the process of reducing data dimensionality for machine learning applications. This process is often necessary because certain attributes, especially in data with high dimension count, could have qualities that impact the learning process of a machine learning model. These qualities include attributes which are highly similar to one another, data that contains a high degree of noise, and attributes that have no or minimal correlation with the target variables that the model is attempting to predict.

To this end, feature selection solutions utilize a variety of different methodologies and strategies. For instance, the applied methodology depends on whether the records in the dataset are classified. In supervised learning, all samples are already in possession of a class label. Several feature selection solutions take advantage of labeling by examining the relation between a given feature and the label itself [3]. In unsupervised machine learning, the additional difficulty of labeling samples is present. A possible solution lies in implementing distance-based classification measures, such as k-Nearest-Neighbours [4]. Novel methods include utilizing adaptive graph methods [5]. In semi-supervised learning, a mix of labelled and unlabelled data is present. Potential solutions include methods based on co-training, graphs or Support-Vector Machines [6]. Another aspect is the search

strategy, of which there traditionally have been three main methods: filter, wrapper, and embedded methods. Filter methods apply solutions that examine the characteristics of the given dataset. These include information theory, univariate statistic measures, and random forest among others [7]. Wrapper methods incorporate machine learning algorithms that evaluate a candidate subset of features and modify this subset accordingly. Examples of these methods are forward selection, backward selection and recursive selection. Embedded methods combine filter and wrapper methods by combining feature selection and machine learning.

Solutions may also vary depending on the specifics of the data in question. Relevant to supervised machine learning, datasets can be described by data labelling, number of classes, sparsity of data, number of features and its data type. Data may be labelled, which means that a sample may have multiple labels that are attached to it. However, a given sample can only be part of one class. Assuming that the values of the target variables are in the discrete domain, the number of such unique values determines whether the dataset is for multivariate or binary classification - with more than two unique values or two unique values, respectively. Otherwise, if the values are continuous, the dataset presents a regression problem.

2.2. Measures for feature selection

Feature selection algorithms are based on a variety of measures, that provide an underlying mechanism to work with. This section lists several popular measures used in feature selection alongside relevant algorithms.

2.2.1 Information theory

Originally, a theory developed for the study of communication and information theory became a ubiquitous concept in several fields of machine learning, including feature selection. At the core of information theory is entropy, conceived by Claude Shannon in 1948 [8]. This measure is accordingly often called Shannon entropy. The formula is as follows:

$$H(X) = - \sum_{x \in X} p(x) \cdot \log p(x),$$

where X denotes the alphabet containing several variables, denoted by x . As the formula suggests, entropy is a measure of uncertainty. Events that are less likely to occur

carry greater information value, as opposed to events happening with higher frequency.

As the basis of information theory lies in probability theory, conditional entropy can be defined via conditional probability. Conditional entropy is therefore:

$$H(X|Y) = - \sum_{x \in X, y \in Y} p(x, y) \cdot \log \frac{p(x, y)}{p(y)}$$

Using these two definitions, the measure of mutual information or information gain can be formulated.

$$MI(X, Y) = H(X) - H(X|Y) = H(Y) - H(Y|X)$$

Mutual information shows the common information content between two alphabets, often portrayed by the intersection of two sets in a Venn diagram. However, a more direct and straightforward visualization is presented in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Mutual information (I) in relation to other information theory quantities. The figure is sourced from the book Information Theory, Inference and Learning Algorithms by David J. C. MacKay [9].

In feature selection, mutual information can be used to determine the degree of redundancy between features or the relevance of a feature to the target variable. It is a core concept in many algorithms presented below.

Forward feature selection algorithm

Amiri et al. [10] proposed an algorithm that filters features based on their mutual information value with the target variable, called Forward Feature Selection Algorithm (FFSA). In each iteration, the candidate feature with the maximum mutual information is added to the set of selected features until the user-defined set size is achieved. The pseudocode of the algorithm can be found in Code 1.

While this algorithm is decent at showing the degree of correlation between a candidate feature and the target, the redundancy between features in the selected set is not accounted for.

Algorithm 1: Pseudocode of FFSA

```
1 Parameters: F: feature set, k: number of features to select, y: target;  
2 Return: S: selected feature set;  
3  $S \leftarrow \{\}$ ;  
4 while  $size(S) < k$  do  
5    $maxIndex \leftarrow 0$ ;  
6   for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $size(F)$  do  
7     if  $MutualInfo(F[maxIndex], y) < MutualInfo(F[i], y)$  then  
8        $maxIndex \leftarrow i$ ;  
9     end  
10  end  
11   $S \leftarrow S + \{F[maxIndex]\}$ ;  
12   $F \leftarrow F - \{F[maxIndex]\}$ ;  
13 end
```

Modified Mutual Information-based Feature Selection Algorithm (MMIFS)

Addressing the question of redundancy between selected features, *Amiri et al.* [10] also proposed a modified version of the Mutual Information-based Feature Selection (MIFS) originally made by *Battiti* [11]. When evaluating a candidate feature for selection, the average of all mutual information values between the candidate and the already selected features is subtracted from the mutual information value of the candidate feature and the target. The measure of penalty can be adjusted by a user-defined parameter β . The pseudocode of the algorithm is presented below in Code 2.

Fast Correlation-Based Filter (FCBF)

Inspired by the concept of statistical correlation, *Yu et al.* [12] proposed an algorithm that uses an information-theoretic approach via utilizing symmetrical uncertainty (SU).

$$SU(X, Y) = 2 \cdot \frac{MI(X|Y)}{H(X) + H(Y)}$$

The algorithm operates on the principle of measuring SU among the features and also the target, similarly to MMIFS. However, unlike the latter which builds a set of selection from zero, FCBF eliminates candidate features in a backward manner. First, SU is calculated between all features and the target as an initial filtering and ranking

Algorithm 2: Pseudocode of MMIFS

```
1 Parameters: F: feature set, k: number of features to select,  $\beta$ : redundancy
   penalty, y: target;
2 Return: S: selected feature set;
3  $S \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
4 while  $size(S) < k$  do
5    $scores \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
6   for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $size(F)$  do
7      $penalty \leftarrow 0$ ;
8     for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $size(S)$  do
9        $penalty \leftarrow penalty + MutualInfo(F[i], S[j])$ ;
10    end
11     $penalty \leftarrow \frac{penalty}{size(S)}$ ;
12     $score \leftarrow MutualInfo(F[i], y) - \beta \cdot penalty$ ;
13     $scores \leftarrow scores + score$ ;
14  end
15   $selectedIndex \leftarrow argmax(scores)$ ;
16   $S \leftarrow S + \{F[selectedIndex]\}$ ;
17   $F \leftarrow F - \{F[selectedIndex]\}$ ;
18 end
```

method. Any features below the user-defined threshold are eliminated from selection. Afterwards, the features are ranked in descending order according to their SU value, the highest valued called the dominant feature. In the second step, features that have higher SU with the dominant feature than the target are dropped from the set of selection. After all features below the dominant feature were examined, the dominance is given to the next feature with the highest SU value and the same filtering method is repeated. The algorithm concludes once there are no more features that can assume dominance.

This solution addresses a number of shortcomings of linear correlation, such as the inability to deal with non-numerical or non-linear data. A downside of this implementation is the absence of defining the size of the selected feature set. The pseudocode of the algorithm is located in Code 3.

Algorithm 3: Pseudocode of FCBF

```
1 Parameters:  $F$ : feature set,  $\delta$ : initial filter threshold,  $y$ : target;
2 Return:  $S$ : selected feature set;
3  $S \leftarrow F$ ;
4  $SUvalues \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
5 for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $size(S)$  do
6    $fSU \leftarrow SymUn(S[i], y)$ ;
7   if  $fSU < \delta$  then
8      $S \leftarrow S - \{S[i]\}$ ;
9   else
10     $SUvalues \leftarrow SUvalues + \{fSU\}$ ;
11  end
12 end
13  $SUvalues \leftarrow orderDescending(SUvalues)$ ;
14  $S \leftarrow orderBy(S, SUvalues)$ ;
15  $size \leftarrow size(S)$ ;
16  $i \leftarrow 0$ ;
17 while  $i < size$  do
18   for  $j \leftarrow size - 1$  to  $i$  do
19     if  $SUvalues[j] < SymUn(S[i], S[j])$  then
20        $S \leftarrow S - \{S[j]\}$ ;
21        $SUvalues \leftarrow SUvalues - \{SUvalues[j]\}$ ;
22        $size \leftarrow size - 1$ ;
23     end
24   end
25    $i \leftarrow i + 1$ ;
26 end
```

Fast Correlation-Based Filter # (FCBF#)

Targeting the inability to determine the size of the selected feature set in the original FCBF, *Senliol et al.* [13] introduced a modified version of the algorithm that also changes the search strategy. Instead of eliminating all possible features, the dominant feature may filter out only one feature before giving the dominance over to the next feature. While the modification resulted in an increase in runtime, the more balanced nature of elimination showed increased scores during evaluation. The pseudocode is presented in Code 4.

Minimum Redundancy - Maximum Relevance (MRMR)

As one of the core concepts in feature selection is the elimination of redundant features, *Ding et al.* [14] developed a solution that seeks features with the minimum similarity between the already selected features and the maximum relevance with the target using mutual information.

The degree of redundancy between features is measured by:

$$W = \frac{1}{|S|^2} \cdot \sum_{i,j \in S} MI(i, j),$$

where S denotes the set of selected features.

The degree of relevance between features and the target is measured by:

$$V = \frac{1}{|S|} \cdot \sum_{i \in S} MI(i, y),$$

where S denotes the set of selected features and y the target vector.

A score can be formulated based on either the difference or the quotient of these two measures. The goal of the algorithm is finding a subset of features that maximizes this score:

$$\max(V - W), \max(V/W)$$

The pseudocode of this algorithm can be found in Code 5.

Joint Mutual Information Maximization (JMIM)

Yang et al. [15] proposed an algorithm that is based on calculating the joint mutual information for every feature pair and the target. The features that return with the highest JMI are selected.

Algorithm 4: Pseudocode of FCBF#

```
1 Parameters: F: feature set, k: number of features to select,  $\delta$ : initial filter
   threshold, y: target;
2 Return: S: selected feature set;
3  $S \leftarrow F$ ;
4  $SUvalues \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
5 for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $size(S)$  do
6    $fSU \leftarrow SymUn(S[i], y)$ ;
7   if  $fSU < \delta$  then
8      $S \leftarrow S - \{S[i]\}$ ;
9   else
10     $SUvalues \leftarrow SUvalues + \{fSU\}$ ;
11  end
12 end
13  $SUvalues \leftarrow orderDescending(SUvalues)$ ;
14  $S \leftarrow orderBy(S, SUvalues)$ ;
15  $size \leftarrow size(S)$ ;
16  $i \leftarrow 0$ ;
17 while  $i < size$  and  $size > k$  do
18   for  $j \leftarrow size - 1$  to  $i$  do
19     if  $SUvalues[j] < SymUn(S[i], S[j])$  then
20        $S \leftarrow S - \{S[j]\}$ ;
21        $SUvalues \leftarrow SUvalues - \{SUvalues[j]\}$ ;
22        $size \leftarrow size - 1$ ;
23     break;
24   end
25 end
26  $i \leftarrow i + 1$ ;
27 end
```

Algorithm 5: Pseudocode of MRMR

```
1 Parameters: F: feature set, k: number of features to select, y: target;
2 Return: S: selected feature set;
3  $S \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
4 while  $size(S) < k$  do
5    $scores \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
6   for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $size(F)$  do
7      $redun \leftarrow 0$ ;
8     for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $size(S)$  do
9        $redun \leftarrow redun + MutualInfo(F[i], S[j])$ ;
10    end
11     $redun \leftarrow \frac{redun}{size(S)^2}$ ;
12    if scoring method is difference then
13       $score \leftarrow MutualInfo(F[i], y) - redun$ ;
14    else
15       $score \leftarrow MutualInfo(F[i], y) / redun$ ;
16    end
17     $scores \leftarrow scores + score$ ;
18  end
19   $selectedIndex \leftarrow argmax(scores)$ ;
20   $S \leftarrow S + \{F[selectedIndex]\}$ ;
21   $F \leftarrow F - \{F[selectedIndex]\}$ ;
22 end
```

2.2.2 Correlation

Statistical correlation measures provide a solid basis for exploring the relationship between two variables. One such method is the Pearson correlation coefficient with the following formula:

$$r(X, Y) = \frac{\sum_{x \in X, y \in Y} (x - m_x) \cdot (y - m_y)}{\sqrt{\sum_{x \in X} (x - m_x)^2 \cdot \sum_{y \in Y} (y - m_y)^2}},$$

where X and Y denote two vectors, while m_x and m_y represent the means of X and Y respectively.

Linear Correlation-based Feature Selection Algorithm (LCFS)

Similar to the Modified Mutual Information-based Feature Selection Algorithm, *Amiri et al.* [10] proposed replacing the mutual information measure in the MMIFS algorithm with Pearson's linear correlation coefficient. While only able to efficiently evaluate linear relationships, the algorithm is computationally less demanding than its information-theoretic counterpart. The pseudocode is presented below in Code 6.

Algorithm 6: Pseudocode of LCFS

```
1 Parameters: F: feature set, k: number of features to select,  $\beta$ : redundancy
   penalty, y: target;
2 Return: S: selected feature set;
3  $S \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
4 while  $size(S) < k$  do
5    $scores \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
6   for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $size(F)$  do
7      $penalty \leftarrow 0$ ;
8     for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $size(S)$  do
9        $penalty \leftarrow penalty + Corr(F[i], S[j])$ ;
10    end
11     $penalty \leftarrow \frac{penalty}{size(S)}$ ;
12     $score \leftarrow Corr(F[i], y) - \beta \cdot penalty$ ;
13     $scores \leftarrow scores + score$ ;
14  end
15   $selectedIndex \leftarrow argmax(scores)$ ;
16   $S \leftarrow S + \{F[selectedIndex]\}$ ;
17   $F \leftarrow F - \{F[selectedIndex]\}$ ;
18 end
```

2.2.3 Distance

Distance-based measures are already widespread in several fields of machine learning, such as classification in unsupervised or semi-supervised learning. In feature selection, the distance between features and the target determines the similarity. Measures like Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, and Canberra distance offer different approaches

to forming solutions. The former two are also known as part of the Minkowski family of metrics, as they can be generalized with a single change in parameter:

$$D(X, Y) = \left(\sum_{x \in X, y \in Y} |x - y|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}},$$

where X and Y denote the vectors and $p = 2$ provides the formula for the Euclidean distance, while $p = 1$ equals the Manhattan distance.

Several variations of the Manhattan distance exist in literature, one of them being the Canberra distance. The goal of the modification is the normalization of the distance by dividing with the sum of the coordinate's absolute values:

$$CD(X, Y) = \sum_{x \in X, y \in Y} \frac{|x - y|}{|x| + |y|},$$

where X and Y denote the vectors [16].

Euclidean distance (EUDI)

Implemented in the AHFS framework as an algorithm, EUDI utilizes Euclidean distance as a measure to determine the similarity of same-class samples, with features providing additional dimensions and coordinates with each addition. The combination of features in a k -size subset that provides the best score is selected.

In the first part, samples in the same class have their class mean calculated. The candidate features act as coordinate dimensions. Then, the distance of each sample to this mean position is averaged.

In the second part, the mean of all samples, regardless of class, is established. Then, the average distance between the previously calculated class means and the mean of all samples is recorded.

Finally, in the third part, the second score is divided by the first score. The higher the resulting value, the better the combination of features involved performed.

2.3. Search algorithms

2.3.1 Genetic algorithms

Genetic algorithms are computational models of biological evolution. They are primarily based on natural selection. Initially, the search begins by generating a swarm or population. The population consists of individuals and individuals themselves contain

genes that can undergo mutation. In each iteration of the algorithm, individuals are evaluated based on an arbitrary metric. Then, a pre-defined upper percentage of individuals are retained, while the rest are discarded. The surviving population produce children that inherit a crossover of their parents' genes. After crossover, the children are subject to mutation, which further varies their genetic makeup [17].

In feature selection, the individual is a feature subset and genes are features. While several variations of genetic algorithms exist for feature selection, they all adhere to the principles mentioned above [18].

2.3.2 Sequential Forward Selection (SFS)

Sequential Forward Selection is a search strategy that builds a set of selection starting from an empty set. Selecting the next item is based on a prior evaluation. Once selected, the item stays in the selection set, no elimination occurs [2].

Chapter 3

Proposed solution

This chapter presents the proposed solution. In Section 1, the original Adaptive Hybrid Feature Selection (AHFS) algorithm is detailed. In Section 2, the modified aspects of the AHFS algorithm are presented. Finally, in Section 3, all relevant parameters are shown.

3.1. Adaptive Hybrid Feature Selection

3.1.1 Overview

As no feature selection algorithm or measure exists that can universally be applied to every machine learning problem, there is a need for a solution that can provide a more generalized approach that individual algorithms are not capable of delivering. *Viharos et al.* [2] proposed an algorithmic framework that incorporates multiple feature selection algorithms based on various measures. This hybrid nature of the solution allows an adaptive approach when selecting features. A neural network iterates through the proposed candidates and evaluates them based on a metric. The feature that performed the best is selected and included in further selection. The algorithm concludes once the user-defined size of the feature subset is reached. A basic flowchart of the algorithm is presented in Figure 3.1.

The AHFS algorithm is applicable for binary or multivariate classification problems on non-sparse numeric datasets. While it cannot handle regression tasks, discretization of the continuous target variables is a potential workaround.

3.1.2 Search strategy

The search strategy is defined as Sequential Forward Selection (SFS). In each iteration of the algorithm, after evaluating all candidates, the feature that provided the best model

Figure 3.1: Flowchart of the AHFS algorithm.

together with the previously selected features is incorporated into the set of selected features.

Figure 3.2 illustrates the method well. The boxes represent features with their respective index within. Features 13 and 8 were selected in the previous two iterations. The arrows visualize the algorithms that recommend the feature subset pointed at, each column being a different suggestion. One algorithm suggests one subset. Note that the features marked black remain in the selected subset, no backward elimination occurs at any time. Once evaluated by the neural network, the feature marked green is integrated into the selected set as its subset produced the most favorable result.

Figure 3.2: Sequential Forward Selection in AHFS. The image is sourced from the original article.

3.1.3 Evaluation

Evaluation of candidate features is done via an artificial neural network, making the AHFS algorithm a wrapper method. The evaluation method is arbitrary and can be changed or modified as needed. While not the subject of this report, the choice of evaluation is another possible venue of improvement for the algorithm.

3.1.4 Measures

The framework contains several information-theoretic, one correlation-based, and one distance-based measure. It is worth noting that the framework can be expanded with virtually any number of feature selection algorithms and measures.

3.1.5 Discretization

If any of the features or the target variable is continuous in nature, discretization is performed. A user-defined number of uniform-width intervals called bins are established between the minimum and the maximum value. Any values that fall into the interval is assigned the index of that bin. While a greater number of bins results in increased prediction accuracy, the increase in bins correlate with an increased time demand.

3.1.6 Superiority and limits

The expanded range of candidate features enables the algorithm to produce models highly accurate compared to individual feature selection algorithms, as seen in Figure

3.3. Consequently, there is a major increase in time demand.

Figure 3.3: Average performance of the AHFS versus individual algorithms. Image sourced from the original article.

3.2. Enhanced aspects

The SFS method is entirely replaced with a genetic approach. This results in a modified mode of operation, which is shown in Figure 3.4.

In this version, measures are only run once to provide the initial number of feature subsets. Following evaluation, the best n subsets are kept, and their features are pooled together into a set. This set is then shuffled and provides as many subsets as many can be formed, with each feature being used only once. If the number of features is not enough to form a subset, random features are added until the necessary number is met. Note that the original subsets are kept.

Following the crossover phase, each feature in every subset has a certain chance to mutate and be replaced with another feature not within its own set. If mutation occurs, the original set is preserved and copied. The mutation will occur in the copy.

3.3. Parameters

3.3.1 Neural network

The artificial neural network was implemented in the framework of TensorFlow's Keras module [19] [20]. The ANN is a *Sequential* model with two layers. Layer 1 is a *Dense* layer with eight neurons. Layer 2 is an *Output* layer with the number of classes as the number of neurons. Values are normalized between 0.1 and 0.9 before both layer. The model

Figure 3.4: Flowchart of the modified AHFS algorithm.

uses the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.1. Early stopping is implemented at 20 epochs. The evaluation metric used is mean-squared error. Stratified K-Fold provides the splitting of the data into train and test sets with 3 folds.

3.3.2 Genetic algorithm

Following the evaluation of each subset, the best 2 performing feature subsets are retrieved. Each feature has a 10% chance of getting replaced by another feature via mutation.

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter presents the results of the implementation of the genetic search algorithm in the Adaptive Hybrid Feature Selection algorithm. In Section 1, the evaluation datasets are explored. In Section 2, the methodology and results are presented in detail. In Section 3, the findings are discussed.

4.1. Evaluation datasets

Two datasets from the UC Irvine Machine Learning Repository (UCI MLR) were chosen to assess the effectiveness of the genetic algorithm.

Forest Fires (forestfires) [21] is a regression-task dataset with 517 instances and 12 features. The objective is to estimate the burned area of a forest. This dataset was chosen to demonstrate the capabilities of the genetic algorithm when deployed in small dimensions. The target variable was discretized into 4 bins to provide a relatively reliable prediction while keeping down time demand.

Connectionist Bench - Sonar, Mines vs. Rocks [22] is a classification-task dataset with 208 instances and 60 features. The objective is to predict whether returning sonar signals are bouncing off rocks or metal cylinders. This dataset was chosen for its higher feature count.

4.2. Methodology and results

First, categorical features were enumerated and continuous values were discretized to ensure compatibility with the AHFS algorithm. Secondly, the AHFS with SFS processed the datasets and set up an order of features that kept increasing the subset size in every iteration. The metric used was mean squared error (MSE). The results are presented in

Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Model error rates for both datasets. The red lines represent subset boundaries used later when comparing the SFS implementation to the genetic algorithm. Due to size constraints, only every second selected feature is presented on the horizontal axis of the sonar dataset.

Due to time constraints, three subsets were considered for comparison against the genetic algorithm. In *forestfires*, features 8 – 1, 8 – 9, and 8 – 7 made up subsets of size 6, 8, and 10, respectively. In *sonar*, features 10 – 14 of size 4, 10 – 55 of size 18, and 10 – 12 of size 48. Recall, that selected features in an iteration also contain features selected in the previous iterations, forming a subset. For instance These boundaries share in common that they represent either local or global extreme values of MSE.

The genetic algorithm was run on these subset sizes. The results are presented in Figure 4.2.

Feature subsets that resulted in the lowest model error were selected to be compared against the candidate subset of the SFS algorithm. The three pairs of subsets were run 10 times to measure average error and standard deviation. The findings are presented below in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.2: All genetic algorithm runs with different parameters.

4.3. Interpretation of results

The genetic search algorithm failed to present improved model error rates compared to the global minimums of the SFS algorithm. However, the findings suggest that the genetic algorithm could improve results where SFS error rates start increasing. In addition, a greater feature space combined with an increased iteration count would allow more possibilities for the genetic search algorithm to explore. Due to time constraints, the full extent of this algorithm could not be tested.

Figure 4.3: Results of the comparisons. The global minimum found by the SFS algorithm is the middle feature.

Chapter 5

Conclusion and future research

The aim of this research was to implement a genetic search algorithm into the Adaptive Hybrid Feature Selection algorithm with the purpose of decreasing model error rates. By replacing the Sequential Forward Selection search algorithm, the greedy nature of SFS could be avoided. The implementation was tested on two structurally different datasets with one set of parameters. In the current environment, the genetic algorithm was largely inferior to the SFS algorithm.

However, the genetic algorithm has shown potential in decreasing model error rates for certain feature subset sizes where the model provided by the SFS algorithm became increasingly unreliable. In the future, this avenue of approach should be explored further.

Furthermore, the AHFS algorithm presents many opportunities for future work. Other search strategies, such as simulated annealing, could be implemented. The neural network for feature subset evaluation could be replaced with a more time-efficient and accurate model. Additional measures may be added to the already existing list.

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